

THE IMPORTANCE OF READING SKILLS IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF COMPREHENSION SKILLS IN BEGINNER-LEVEL YOUNG LEARNERS

Yunusova Sojida

The English teacher of Jizzakh academic lyceum of The Ministry of Internal Affairs

Abduraximova Mashhura

1st year postgraduate of Foreign languages department of Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

Annotation

This article covers the importance of reading skills in the development of comprehension skills such as vocabulary, inference, prediction, explain, retrieval in primary school-aged children, and the implementation of this process is shown on the example of interactive games.

Keywords: reading, critical thinking, creativity, imagination, comprehension skills, vocabulary, retrieval, inference.

Developing reading skills in young children can help them develop other skills as well. Reading requires comprehension, critical thinking, and analytical skills, which can lay the groundwork for learning English language. Developing reading skills can also lead to the development of language skills, including grammar and vocabulary, and building an understanding of different contexts. Additionally, reading can help children develop empathy, as well as creativity and imagination, as they explore different worlds and other perspectives through literature. Furthermore, reading can help boost self-esteem and confidence levels, as children gain a better understanding of the world around them.

Developing reading skills among young children is important for many reasons. It helps foster a love of reading early on, which can give them a greater understanding of the language they use to communicate with others. Reading also helps develop a child's critical thinking and analytical skills, as well as their comprehension abilities. Learning how to read can also help children prepare for future educational endeavors, and it can open up the world of literature and imagination. Furthermore, reading can support mental well-being, as it can be an enjoyable form of self-expression. So, developing reading skills early on can set children up for greater success in the future.

Comprehension skills are critical for primary school-aged children because they help them to make sense of complex texts and information. By actively engaging in comprehension tasks such as making inferences, summarizing, understanding story elements, or determining causes and effects, children build their ability to read with understanding.

This enhanced ability gives them better insight into the material they are reading, which helps them to excel academically.

Additionally, strong comprehension skills encourage students to learn and explore new ideas independently rather than simply following instructions or memorizing facts from a textbook. Ultimately, comprehensive education promotes higher academic achievement levels in all study areas.

So, what are the VIPER comprehension skills? We can see the role of reading skill in the development of VIPER comprehension skills below.

Vocabulary

Teaching children how to identify correct vocabulary when using their comprehension skills is crucial in their education. To start, teachers can select several texts that contain multiple Tier 3 vocabularies that the students may not yet know.

The teacher should then find a way to present these words in a meaningful

context- perhaps through a class discussion or by breaking into small groups for a roundtable analysis of each term.

Teachers can leverage technology and resources such as online flashcards and games to provide visual reinforcements for the terms. Overall, teaching a child how to recognize and use correct vocabulary as part of their comprehension skills is best accomplished through a mix of activities that force active reading and engagement with the material while still allowing them to take breaks and focus on more gaming-oriented activities.

Inference

When it comes to teaching children about inference, one of the best tools for educators is storyboarding. Storyboarding allows teachers to provide students with engaging scenarios that can help them practice making beliefs.

Through open-ended questions and prompts related to the stories, teachers can provide students with opportunities to think critically and make inferences by identifying patterns, drawing conclusions, and using other critical thinking skills.

Activities such as roleplaying can also be used to promote inference and allow students to discuss their inferences with peers in a safe learning environment. Ultimately, using these strategies can help guide and teach children of all ages how to effectively use inference when improving their comprehension skills.

Prediction

Teaching children to predict is an important part of developing their comprehension skills. Teachers should provide them with opportunities to practice making predictions throughout daily learning activities and in story settings.

An effective way to start is by helping children form specific questions as they read a text, encouraging them to think more deeply and gain more meaning from the content.

To refine their prediction practices, teachers could also ask students to analyze characters' thoughts and feelings, generate statements about how events may unfold based on textual cues, or draw conclusions from the texts presented.

For example, through discussion, teachers could ask students what might happen next in a story after establishing a specific context. By propelling students to practice these prediction skills during creative reading activities, teachers can help them recognize story patterns and become better readers overall.

Explain

Teaching children how to explain their answers when responding to reading questions is an important part of the literacy process. It can help them work more independently and think more deeply about their understanding of the text.

To do so, teachers should spend time discussing the source material, examining the context from which it was taken, and highlighting key ideas and evidence in the text that support different points of view.

By focusing on discussing evidence and implications together, teachers can foster a classroom environment where students are comfortable expressing their own ideas without fear of judgement. As children practice answering questions about a text and become more familiar with expressing themselves, they will be able to better articulate their thoughts, feelings, and understandings of what they have read.

Retrieval

Teaching children how to answer retrieval-style questions can help them build essential skills like understanding keywords and developing their ability to identify direct quotations.

One great way for teachers to accomplish this is by having students craft various response sentences in pairs or small groups after they have read a passage designated by the teacher, such as a short story or poem.

Once all of the students have formed their sentences, the teacher can lead a discussion on the language used and how it differs from paraphrasing.

Retrieval-style questions are a type of question that is designed to assess pupils' knowledge of a specific topic. These questions require students to recall previously learned material, processes, or facts, and can take a variety of forms, including multiple choice, true/false, fill-in-the-blank, and matching. Retrieval-style questions are often used in educational settings to test pupils' knowledge of a specific topic, and can encourage students to actively engage with course materials.

This exercise will show the children examples that clearly illustrate the differences between summarizing, quoting and paraphrasing so that when it comes time for them to answer retrieval-style questions, they can better identify direct quotations from a text and assign proper authorship.

Summarise

Teaching children to summarise requires first introducing them to the concept. Start by providing them with short texts and having them summarize a paragraph or section in a few sentences. As their skills improve, have students practice summarizing longer texts into one or two sentences.

Practising with different text genres, such as fiction and non-fiction, will make them more confident when answering summarising-style questions on tests. To further practice, allow children to create their own summaries of the stories they are reading in class.

This activity will also help them better understand the story they are reading while developing an understanding of how to concisely summarise information.

The formation of reading skills is one of the most important components of the process of teaching English at all its stages. Reading refers to receptive types of speech activity, enters into the sphere of communicative and social activity of people and provides a written form of communication in it.

The initial stage of learning to read has as its goal the formation of students' reading techniques in a foreign language and, in particular, such abilities as:

- quick establishment of sound and letter matches;
- correct scoring of the graphic image of the word and its correlation with the meaning, i.e. understanding / comprehension of what is read;
- reading by combining words into specific semantic groups;
- reading at a natural pace of texts based on familiar language material;
- expressive reading of texts by ear, with the correct stress and intonation;
- quick establishment of sound and letter matches;
- correct scoring of the graphic image of the word and its correlation with the meaning, i.e. understanding / comprehension of what is read;
- reading by combining words into specific semantic groups;
- reading at a natural pace of texts based on familiar language material;
- expressive reading of texts by ear, with the correct stress and intonation.

As an example, it can be *Running dictation*.

This lively activity uses texts to practise reading and other skills as speaking, listening and writing.

- Choose a short text. Put several copies of the text up around the walls of the classroom (or even the school building).

- Put the learners in pairs.

- The aim is for one of the learners in each team to walk (or run!) to read the text on the wall. They memorise some of the text (three or four words), return to their partner and dictate what they remember. Their partner writes the text.

- Learners swap roles when the teacher shouts ‘Change!’ Over several turns they build the whole text.
- The winner is the team that finishes first.
- Learners compare their writing with the text and make any corrections.
- Use the text for the next part of the lesson; for example, questions about the text, a discussion.

In place of the conclusion, it can be said that, reading is a vital skill that all young learners should be taught. Reading provides a strong base for building other language skills, as well as providing insights into the world outside their own. Educators should strive to expose pupils to different texts and genres, help them develop reading comprehension and vocabulary skills, and utilize technology to create engaging and interactive learning experiences. In addition, teachers should provide ample opportunities for students to practice their reading skills in the real world. With the right skills and instruction, all young learners can become strong readers and gain a deeper understanding of language.

References

1. Turgunova Sh.T. TEACHING READING IN ENGLISH LESSON. ВЕСТНИК НАУКИ И ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ № 7 (85). Часть 2. 2020. – 73 p.
2. Vaysburd M.L. Requirements for texts for independent (synthetic) reading in English in the VII grade. M., 1955.
3. Vaysburd M.L., Blokhina S.A. Learning to understand a foreign language text while reading as a search activity // Foreign languages at school, 1997. № 1-2. P. 33-38.
4. <https://theteachingcouple.com/the-importance-of-comprehension-skills-in-primary-school/>